

Right of Access under Article 15 GDPR: Evasive Compliance and Article 12(1) Transparency

Author: Yana Bondarieva

Type: Working Paper/ Preprint

Access right: Open Access

ORCID ID: 0009-0009-5660-5985

Affiliation: Independent researcher in GDPR and AI compliance

Date: 04 May 2026

License: Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

Keywords GDPR, Article 15, right of access, Article 12, evasive compliance, Österreichische Post, CRIF, EDPB Guidelines 01/2022, right of access quality.

Abstract

Article 15 GDPR grants data subjects the right of access to their personal data and to the information listed regarding its processing. The EDPB Guidelines 01/2022 clarify the procedure for exercising this right, while the 2023 judgments of the Court of Justice of the EU — Österreichische Post (C-154/21), CRIF (C-487/21), Pankki S (C-579/21), FT v DW (C-307/22) — have partially clarified what must be included in the response.

However, a problem remains: while the law establishes that a controller must respond to a data subject's request without undue delay and within one month, the GDPR does not impose an explicit obligation to align the content of the response with the content of the data subject's request. In practice, controllers often respond formally but not substantively.

This work identifies three ways in which controllers evade providing a meaningful response: (1) procedural deflection; (2) topic substitution (response not addressing the question asked); (3) useless response — information is provided but is not usable for the exercise of subsequent rights. Each method is illustrated by a reference case based on documented but anonymised correspondence with a data controller.

The work argues that such responses may be considered a violation of Article 12(1) GDPR (requirement for clear and understandable language), supported by additional EDPB clarifications and coordinated supervisory practice; in the long term, it suggests embedding a standard of specificity and usability of responses directly into Article 15 GDPR.

Keywords: GDPR, Article 15, right of access, Article 12, evasive compliance, Österreichische Post, CRIF, EDPB Guidelines 01/2022, right of access quality.

Introduction

The right of access is the foundation of all data subject rights. Without access to information about how data are processed, a data subject cannot object, request erasure, or verify the lawfulness of processing. Recital 63 GDPR explicitly states that the right of access exists in

order to allow individuals to be aware of and verify the lawfulness of processing. This right should be exercised easily and at reasonable intervals, to obtain confirmation and information about processing.

Article 15 GDPR grants the data subject the right to obtain confirmation as to whether personal data concerning them are being processed and, where that is the case, access to those data as well as to the information listed in the provision. In particular, the data subject has the right to information on the purposes of processing, categories of personal data, recipients, storage periods, data sources, the existence of automated decision-making, and safeguards for transfers to third countries. The Court of Justice of the EU in a series of 2023 judgments clarified the interpretation of certain elements of Article 15 GDPR.

However, Article 15 is silent on one issue: whether the controller must respond specifically to the questions posed by the data subject. If a data subject asks specific questions, the controller may provide a single general response — and formally this may still comply with Article 15. In practice, controllers often respond in general, vague, and procedural terms, without addressing the substance of the questions, thereby fulfilling only the formal requirement of responding within the deadline.

In this work, this behaviour is referred to as “evasive compliance”, meaning formal compliance with GDPR requirements without achieving their functional purpose. The following sections describe three ways in which controllers evade responding. All three are illustrated by a reference case — documented but anonymised correspondence with a data controller. The conclusion formulates three recommendations for the EDPB, national supervisory authorities, and the European legislator.

Purpose of the Right of Access

The right of access serves three purposes:

1. To determine whether personal data are being processed at all.
2. To verify lawfulness: whether there is a legal basis (Article 6), whether Articles 13 and 14 are complied with, and whether data are accurate and not excessive.
3. To obtain information necessary to exercise other rights: erasure (Article 17), objection (Article 21), and complaints to a supervisory authority (Article 77).

The third purpose is the most important for this work. If a response states that data are shared with “service providers”, the data subject cannot object to a specific recipient — they simply do not know who it is. A similar issue arises when controllers describe automated decision-making as based on “various factors”: such wording does not allow the data subject to understand the logic of decision-making and therefore to effectively exercise their right to object or request meaningful human intervention under Article 22(3) GDPR. The absence of a substantive response effectively undermines the exercise of all other rights, as it makes their practical enforcement impossible.

Therefore, the quality of the response is not a secondary issue — it determines the functioning of the entire system of data subject rights. This practice also raises concerns regarding compliance with the principle of transparency under Article 5(1)(a) GDPR. The key question is whether the data subject can effectively exercise their rights when needed.

A formally compliant but substantively evasive response may have more severe consequences than a refusal. A refusal can be challenged and reviewed, whereas an evasive response obscures the very subject of protection and makes it more difficult to contest, as it does not clearly indicate whether the right has been restricted.

What the Court of Justice of the EU said in 2023

Throughout 2023, the Court of Justice of the EU dealt with a series of cases that, taken together, shifted the focus of the application of Article 15 GDPR from the formal provision of information towards a requirement of specificity and substantive completeness. The very emergence and consistent consideration of such cases indicates that the issue is not merely theoretical, but of clear practical relevance. It reflects a persistent problem faced by data subjects in practice: the provision of formally correct but insufficiently specific or overly general responses that do not allow them to fully understand how their personal data are being processed or to effectively exercise subsequent data protection rights.

In *Österreichische Post (C-154/21)*, the Court confirmed that a data subject must, in principle, receive information about the recipients of their personal data, and that the use of “categories of recipients” is permissible only in exceptional cases where identification is objectively impossible or the request is manifestly unfounded or excessive. This strengthens the requirement of targeted transparency in data processing.

In *CRIF (C-487/21)*, the Court clarified that a «copy» of personal data must not be understood as a mere formal extract, but as a form of presentation that enables the data subject to genuinely understand its content and the context of processing.

In *Pankki S (C-579/21)*, the Court held that access logs and records of access to personal data may themselves constitute personal data and may, where relevant, fall within the scope of the right of access under Article 15 GDPR.

Finally, in *FT v DW (C-307/22)*, the Court confirmed that the right of access is autonomous in nature and does not depend on the data subject’s motives, including any intention to use the information in a dispute with the controller.

Taken together, these judgments reflect a general trend: the right of access under Article 15 GDPR must ensure not merely the formal disclosure of information, but its functional effectiveness for understanding data processing and for enabling the effective exercise of data subject rights.

EDPB Guidelines 01/2022: Scope and Limits of Regulation

The EDPB Guidelines 01/2022 on the right of access, adopted in their final version on 28 March 2023, constitute the most authoritative interpretation of the practical application of Article 15 GDPR at EU level.

The document confirms a number of key principles deriving from the overall regime of transparency and the effectiveness of data subject rights.

First, the information provided must be formulated in a clear and accessible manner in accordance with Article 12(1) GDPR. This requires not only legal accuracy but also comprehensibility for the data subject.

Second, the controller must take active measures to ensure that the data subject can actually understand the information provided, rather than merely receiving it in a formalised manner.

Third, the use of self-service interfaces (such as online accounts or dashboards) does not relieve the controller of the obligation to provide complete information, where such interfaces do not disclose all elements required under Article 15 GDPR.

Fourth, the right of access may not be arbitrarily restricted by reference to “manifestly unfounded” or “excessive” requests; such exceptions must be interpreted strictly and applied only in exceptional cases.

At the same time, the Guidelines do not impose an obligation to structure the response strictly in accordance with the form of the data subject’s request. In other words, where a data subject asks specific questions, the controller is not required to answer each of them separately, provided that the response as a whole covers the requested information and complies with the requirements of clarity and completeness under Article 12(1) GDPR.

The question of whether the structure of the response must mirror the structure of the data subject’s request is not explicitly regulated, which leaves a certain margin for controller practice, provided that the principles of transparency and comprehensibility are respected.

Typology of Evasive Responses by Controllers

The following section examines three typical approaches that may be encountered in controllers’ responses to requests under Article 15 GDPR and which, in certain cases, result in the absence of a meaningful reply. Each of them reflects a failure along a distinct axis:

- (1) procedural deflection;
- (2) topic substitution (response not addressing the question asked);
- (3) useless response — information is provided but is not usable for the exercise of subsequent rights.

All three approaches are illustrated by a reference case.

Reference Case

On 14 October 2024, a data subject residing in Ireland submitted a request under Articles 13, 14, 15, and 17 GDPR to a large international technology controller. The request was triggered

by the creation of an online advertising account in her name without her knowledge, resulting in approximately €240 being charged to her payment card.

The request contained six specific items for which the data subject sought information:

- (1) contact details of the controller;
- (2) contact details of the Data Protection Officer;
- (3) purposes of processing and legal basis;
- (4) categories of personal data processed;
- (5) recipients of the data;
- (6) source of the data, where it was not obtained from the data subject.

In addition, the data subject requested the erasure of personal data under Article 17 GDPR, cessation of further charges, and reimbursement of the disputed amount.

On 21 October 2024, the controller responded without providing information on any of the requested points. Instead, it provided instructions on how to use a self-service procedure: logging into the account, navigating to settings, and cancelling it, with an indication of the expected refund timeframe.

On the same day, the data subject clarified that she did not have access to the account, as she had not created it, referred to Article 12(1) GDPR, and asked a direct question regarding the controller’s willingness to erase the data and refund the funds.

On 22 October 2024, the controller responded again, stating that the request had been forwarded to a “specialised team” and was under review, without providing any timeline or substantive outcome.

This correspondence illustrates three typical approaches that may lead to the absence of a meaningful response.

Procedural Deflection

In this case, the controller does not provide the requested information but redirects the data subject to a system-based procedural route.

Instead of answering the questions set out under Article 15 GDPR, the data subject is instructed to perform actions within the controller’s interface (for example, logging into an account, changing settings, or submitting a request through a form), or to wait for the request to be processed.

In the Reference Case, the controller’s first response reflected this approach: rather than providing information, it contained instructions on account management. The second response was limited to a statement that the request had been forwarded for review.

As a result, the data subject does not receive the requested information, and the interaction is shifted into the sphere of procedural actions.

Topic Shift (answering a different question)

The second approach occurs where the controller formally responds to the request but, instead of providing the requested information, refers to the status of the handling process.

In the Reference Case, following the data subject’s clarifying question regarding the controller’s willingness to erase personal data and refund the funds, the controller stated that the request had been forwarded to a “specialised team” and was under review, without providing any timeframe or substantive outcome.

In this way, the response shifts from the subject matter of the request to a description of the internal processing stage. While such information relates to the handling of the request, it does not substitute an answer to the substantive question concerning the controller’s actions.

Unusable Response – information is provided but not fit for exercising further rights

The third approach may occur independently of the previous two, including in situations where the controller appears to respond to the substance of the request, but the information provided lacks functional utility for the exercise of the data subject’s rights.

This is reflected in situations where, despite formal relevance to the request, the content of the response does not enable the data subject to use the information for exercising rights under the GDPR.

Such responses may take several forms: the use of broad categories instead of specific data, the aggregation of multiple questions into a single unstructured narrative, or the replacement of clear answers with descriptive or conditional formulations.

Despite formal compliance with the request, such responses fail to provide sufficient specificity for subsequent action by the data subject. In particular, they may hinder the identification of specific data recipients, the substantiation of a controller’s refusal, or the preparation of a meaningful complaint to a supervisory authority.

In other words, information is provided, but it does not fulfil its functional role in ensuring the effective exercise of rights under Article 15 GDPR.

What Supervisory Authorities are Already Doing

Despite the absence of an explicit statutory standard regarding the quality of responses under Article 15 GDPR, recent enforcement practice shows a gradual movement towards its development.

At EU level, this has been reflected in the Coordinated Enforcement Framework (CEF) of the European Data Protection Board. In 2024, the EDPB launched a coordinated investigation on the implementation of the right of access. It involved 30 national supervisory authorities and

covered 1,185 controllers across different sectors. The report published on 16 January 2025 identified a number of systemic issues, including overly formal responses, excessive reliance on exemptions, lack of internal procedures for handling requests, and practical barriers for data subjects. The significance of this document lies in the fact that the effectiveness of the right of access was for the first time addressed as a Europe-wide enforcement priority, rather than as an isolated national issue.

At national level, a more concrete approach can be observed in the practice of the Commission Nationale de l'Informatique et des Libertés (CNIL). In its Enforcement Decision (Délibération) No. SAN-2023-009 of 15 June 2023 against Criteo (fine of €40 million), the regulator held that providing incomplete information and using overly general formulations when describing the purposes of processing does not comply with Article 15 GDPR. This is relevant in the context of the present paper, as it concerns situations where information is formally provided, but its level of abstraction prevents the data subject from effectively exercising subsequent rights.

Taken together, these developments indicate that a more substantive standard of response is already emerging in enforcement practice. However, a uniform formal criterion linking the specificity of the request to the specificity of the response is still absent. As a result, there remains room for practices in which formal compliance with Article 15 GDPR does not necessarily ensure its full effectiveness.

Recommendations

Based on the analysis of the application of Article 15 GDPR and the identified forms of evasive responses, three possible directions for further development of regulation and enforcement can be outlined.

EDPB Guidance on the Quality of Responses

The European Data Protection Board could consider issuing additional guidance under Article 15 GDPR clarifying the requirements regarding the quality of responses in situations where data subjects submit structured and specific requests. In particular, it may be useful to more clearly indicate that providing information in a generalised form that does not allow the response to be mapped to individual elements of the request may not always ensure proper compliance with the right of access.

Within such an approach, the forms of evasive responses described in this paper could be assessed through the lens of Article 12(1) GDPR as potentially problematic in terms of clarity and intelligibility of communication.

Development of Supervisory Practice under Article 12(1) GDPR

National supervisory authorities, within the framework of the EDPB consistency mechanism, could develop a more consistent approach to assessing the quality of responses to data subject requests.

In particular, greater reliance on Article 12(1) GDPR may be considered not only when evaluating the wording of responses, but also their substantive structural adequacy.

The gradual development of a harmonised enforcement practice in this area could contribute to the emergence of more predictable standards as to what constitutes an adequate response to a request under Article 15 GDPR.

Possible Clarification of Article 15 GDPR in the Long Term

In the long term, consideration could be given to clarifying the wording of Article 15 GDPR with regard to the relationship between the content of the request and the structure of the response.

In particular, it may be discussed whether to explicitly recognise an approach under which, where the data subject submits specific questions, the controller is required to provide corresponding specific answers, except in cases where the provision of such information is objectively impossible or restricted under the GDPR.

Conclusion

The right of access under Article 15 GDPR is a fundamental element of the personal data protection framework. The case law of the Court of Justice of the European Union in 2023 and the EDPB Guidelines 01/2022 have further clarified certain aspects of this right and strengthened the requirements for its practical implementation. At the same time, a structural feature of Article 15 remains: it defines the list of information to be provided, but does not establish a direct link between the form of the request and the structure of the response.

This paper has identified three recurring ways in which obtaining a meaningful response may be hindered in practice: a shift towards procedural interaction instead of substantive disclosure, a topic shift away from the subject matter of the request, and the provision of formally relevant but functionally insufficient information. Each of these approaches may formally comply with Article 15 GDPR, while at the same time reducing the practical effectiveness of the right of access.

The analysis shows that the key issue is not Article 15 GDPR itself, but rather the absence of a stable standard for the quality of responses, including their structural correspondence to the data subject's request. In this context, Article 12(1) GDPR becomes particularly relevant, as it establishes requirements of clarity and intelligibility which may serve as a normative basis for assessing not only the language of responses, but also their functional adequacy.

From a practical perspective, this means that when faced with evasive responses, data subjects typically turn to supervisory enforcement mechanisms, where the assessment of compliance with transparency and intelligibility requirements becomes central. For controllers, a key element of good practice remains the structuring of responses in a way that allows the information provided to be directly matched with the data subject's request without the need for additional reconstruction of meaning.

References

Court of Justice of the European Union, *RW v Österreichische Post AG*, Case C-154/21, Judgment of 12 January 2023, ECLI:EU:C:2023:3.

Court of Justice of the European Union, *F.F. v Österreichische Datenschutzbehörde and CRIF GmbH*, Case C-487/21, Judgment of 4 May 2023, ECLI:EU:C:2023:369.

Court of Justice of the European Union, *J.M. v Pankki S*, Case C-579/21, Judgment of 22 June 2023, ECLI:EU:C:2023:501.

Court of Justice of the European Union, *FT v DW*, Case C-307/22, Judgment of 26 October 2023, ECLI:EU:C:2023:811.

European Data Protection Board, *Guidelines 01/2022 on Data Subject Rights — Right of Access*, Version 2.0, adopted on 28 March 2023, Brussels.

European Data Protection Board, *Coordinated Enforcement Framework (CEF) 2024 — Right of Access*, Final Report of 16 January 2025, edpb.europa.eu

Commission Nationale de l'Informatique et des Libertés, *Restricted Committee Decision No. SAN-2023-009 of 15 June 2023 concerning Criteo*, legifrance.gouv.fr

Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation), OJ L 119, 4.5.2016, Articles 5, 12, 13, 14, 15, 17, 22, 77, 82 and Recital 63.

About the Author

Yana Bondarieva is an independent researcher and compliance practitioner working at the intersection of the EU General Data Protection Regulation, EU consumer protection law, and the EU Artificial Intelligence Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689). Her work focuses on the practical functioning of data subject rights, international data transfers under Chapter V GDPR, the architecture of cross-border enforcement through the One-Stop-Shop mechanism, and the interaction between data protection obligations and AI compliance.

ORCID iD: 0009-0009-5660-5985

Contact: available via the Zenodo record associated with this working paper.

Note on the Reference Case

The Reference Case is based on documented correspondence dated 14, 21, and 22 October 2024. The data subject in this case is the author of this paper. The correspondence has been anonymised with respect to the individual customer service representative of the controller and is presented in narrative form for the purposes of academic analysis. The author retains the original correspondence and is prepared to provide redacted copies to reviewers and supervisory authorities upon request.

Disclaimer

This working paper is provided for informational and analytical purposes only. It does not constitute legal advice. The views expressed are those of the author. The author has made reasonable efforts to ensure the accuracy of the information presented as of the date of publication; readers are encouraged to consult the underlying case law, regulations, and authoritative sources when applying the analysis to specific circumstances. Nothing in this work should be interpreted as identifying or alleging wrongdoing by any individual employee of any controller — the typology and analysis are directed at institutional and operational patterns, not at the conduct of specific individuals.